

ANALYSIS OF THE FULFILLMENT OF THE STANDING TIME STANDARDS OF WAGONS AT TECHNICAL STATIONS

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to analyze the implementation of the standard of the value of the indicator of the standing time of wagons at technical stations located in the railway transport network. Analytical expressions of the rationing of the values of the standing time of the wagons were brought. The parameters that were taken into account when establishing the technical norm were analyzed. Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the reasons for ineffective time losses in the work of technical stations are not taken into account. On the example of technical stations under JSC "Uzbekistan Railways", the implementation of the norms of transit and local wagon stand times was analyzed. As a result, wagons were offered to mend the standing time in a daily or shift form. Such rationing makes it possible to more efficiently organize the work of stations, including wagon flows.

Keywords: Technical station, wagon standing time, rationing, transit wagon, local wagon.

The main task of any technical station is to spend a minimum and technologically based amount of time on processing wagon flows and formation of trains from them in optimal mode [1-4, 8-16]. Therefore, one of the most important quality indicators of the operation of these stations is the "time of standing wagons" [1, 2, 9, 10, 12, 13].

Analysis of the effectiveness of the work technology of technical stations using the indicator "wagon standing time" provides an opportunity to assess the quality of the work activity of an entire station [1, 2, 9]. Analysis of the effectiveness of the work technology of technical stations using the indicator "wagon standing time" provides an opportunity to assess the quality of the work activity of an entire station [5-10]. The lower the value of this indicator, the more efficient the operation of the station in the process from the reception to the departure of transit processed and non-processed and local wagons to the station.

Currently, the "wagon standing time" indicators are determined, i.e., transit is recyclable and unprocessed, and using a variety of methods on local wagons [1-4, 8-16]. In particular, the standing time of transit recyclable wagons, which are considered the most basic working indicator of technical stations, is determined using the following analytical expression on the example of the work of the sorting station [1, 2, 9].

$$t_{proc} = t_{rec} + t_{dis} + t_{sp} + t_{dp}, h \quad (1)$$

where t_{rec} – time of the wagons in the receiving park from the moment the train is accepted until the start of the disassembling of the composition, hour; t_{dis} – time to disassemble on the sorting hill, hour;

t_{sp} – time to stand in the wagon sorting park, hour; t_{dp} – the time it takes for the wagons to complete the composition in the departure park or to transport it to the departure park before the train leaves, hours.

The waiting time of wagons in the reception park consists of the following elements:

$$t_{rec.p} = t_{sec/bloc}^{rec.p} + t_{wait}^{proc(rec.p)} + t_{proc}^{rec.p} + t_{wait}^{dis}, h(2)$$

where $t_{sec/bloc}^{rec}$ – time of securing and blocking composition in the reception park, hours; $t_{wait}^{proc(rec.p)}$ – waiting time for composition processing in the reception park, hours; $t_{proc}^{rec.p}$ – processing time after the arrives, hours; t_{wait}^{dis} – disassembling waiting time, hours;

The time the wagons stay in the sorting park includes the following elements:

$$t_{sor} = t_{ass} + t_{wait}^{ass.take} + t_{ass.take}, hour \quad (3)$$

where t_{sor} – time of assembly of wagons on the ways of the sorting park, hours; $t_{wait}^{ass.take}$ – time to form the composition and take it to the departure park, hours. $t_{ass.take}$ – the time of forming the composition and transferring it to the departure park, hours.

The waiting time of wagons in the departure park consists of the following elements

$$t_{dp} = t_{sec/bloc}^{dp} + t_{wait}^{proc(dp)} + t_{proc}^{dp} + t_{s.l} + t_{pr.br.} + t_{wait}^{dp}, h \quad (4)$$

where $t_{sec/bloc}^{dp}$ – time of securing and blocking composition in the departure park, hours; $t_{wait}^{proc(dp)}$ – processing waiting time, hours; t_{proc}^{dp} – train departure processing time, hours; $t_{s.l}$ – time of supplying the

train with a locomotive, hours; $t_{pr.br.}$ – time of providing the train with brakes, hours; t_{wait}^{dp} – waiting time for departure, hours.

The time of non-transit processed carriages at the station is determined by the following expression [1, 4]

$$t_{tr}^{proc} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^l \sum_{j=1}^l U_{ij} t_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^l \sum_{j=1}^l U_{ij}}, h \quad (5)$$

$$t_{attach} = t_{rec.p} + t_{disass} + t_{ass}^{trans} + t_{ass} + t_{wait}^{trans} + t_{trans} + t_{plac}^{unload} + t_{wait}^{unload} + t_{unload} + t_{ass}^{unload} + t_{take} + t_{plac}^{load} + t_{wait}^{load} + t_{load} + t_{ass}^{load} + t_{wait}^{take} + t_{take} + t_{sor} + t_{ass}^{sor.p} + t_{wait}^{t.t.} + t_{t.t.} + t_{take}^{dp} + t_{dp}, h \quad (6)$$

where t_{ass}^{trans} – time of the assembly process in the sorting park (before the transfer of the wagon(s) to the cargo facility), hours; t_{ass} – time of assembling local wagons in the sorting park for several loading points, hours; t_{trans} – transfer time to the load point, hours; t_{plac}^{unload} – placement of wagons at the unloading front, hours; t_{unload} – unloading time from wagons, hours; t_{ass}^{unload} – time to assemble wagons after unloading, hour; t_{trans} – time of moving wagons to another freight front to perform double freight operations, hours; t_{plac}^{load} – placement of wagons at the loading front, hours; t_{load} – time of loading wagons, hours; t_{ass}^{load} – time of assembling wagons after loading, hours; t_{take} – the time of taking the wagons from the loading point to the station road, hour; t_{sor} – time of sorting local wagons according to their designated routes, hour; $t_{ass}^{s.p}$ – the time of assembly on the sorting route to the full composition of the specified destination of the cargo point, hour.

The inter-operational expectations of local wagons are the same as those of transit recyclable wagons [1-4].

Currently, the above (1) - (6) expressions are normalized in accordance with the methods established in the “educational technological process of the work of technical stations” [2, 4, 9].

where U_{ij} – The number of non-recyclable transit wagons received from route i and sent to route, t_{ij} – time of stay of the specified wagons at the station, hours.

The standing time of local wagons in double (load-unload) cargo operations is determined by the following expression [1, 4-6].

The norms of the time of carriages at technical stations are calculated separately for recyclable and non-recyclable and local wagons, taking into account the rational operation technology [2, 4, 9].

In most technical stations, until now, the waiting time of wagons is measured by drawing up the “Station’s daily work schedule” [1-4, 9-13, 15, 16]. According to the data of this “Station’s daily work plan graph”, the train-hour costs are determined to calculate the quality indicators of the station. These costs are calculated by summing the daily train-hours for the station in total and divided into elements. The cost of wagon-hours for waiting for actions is determined separately. As a result, a system of indicators defining the work description of the station is formed.

In such a way of regulating the time of carriages, usually only the parameters of the station’s working volume, technical equipment and work technology are taken into account (Fig. 1) [1-16]. This shows that the existing systems of technical regulation of the time of the wagons do not take into account the influence of the causes of inefficient time losses in the process of processing wagons. This, in turn, creates the need to improve the current standardization methods.

In addition, the technical standard is calculated separately for each month [1-4, 9, 10, 14, 15].

Figure 1. Graph of the dependence of the standing time of wagons on the volume of their processing.

In this t_{tech} depends on the level of technical equipment of the station, in addition to the number of processed wagons. The value of t_{wait} is directly related to the number of cars to be processed [1, 2, 9].

In order to analyze and assess the practical implementation of the technical standards of the time of carriages, the working process of the technical stations of “Uzbekistan Railways” JSC was studied in the period 2012-2021 (Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 2. Dynamics of waiting times of transit wagons at the stations owned by JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" in the period 2012-2021

The results of the current statistical informations show that during the years 2012-2021, transit wagons' waiting times at technical stations owned by JSC "Uzbekistan Railways" were significantly variable. In this (Figure 2), the results (plan and practice) created a big

difference in 2012, that is, almost 10 hours in the plan and 15 hours in practice. Compared to 2012, the gap between the values of these indicators has been reduced during the remaining years.

Figure 3. The dynamics of the time of local wagons in service for one load in the period of 2012-2021 at the stations owned by "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC

During 2012 and 2021, the dynamics of the standing times of local wagons shows that the current standing time indicators were almost 1,5 times higher than the planned value (41,36 and 27,81 hours, respectively), the size of this ratio in turn served as the main factor in the circulation in the cargo flow. As a result of the effort of the relevant responsible employees, 38,42 hours were achieved in practice in 2016 and 40,15 hours in the plan. As of the last year of observations, it was practically 38,70 hours and 37,30 hours in plan.

The performance of the "wagon standing time" indicator at technical stations with the lowest values in practice plays an important role in determining the quality of work of railway transport.

Based on the results of the analysis conducted on the example of the technical stations owned by JSC "Uzbekistan Railways", it was determined that it is appropriate to set the norm of "wagon standing time" not for individual months, but for a day or a shift. Such standardization makes it possible to more efficiently organize the work of stations, including train flows.

References

1. Butunov D.B. Improvement of technical experimental methods for organization of wagon flows and management evaluation at sorting stations. Dis. ... doc. Phil. (PhD). Tashkent: TashIIT. – 2019. – 187 p.
2. Dilmurod Butunov Baxodirovich, Sokijon Khudayberganov Kobiljonovich, Shinpolat Suyunbaev

Mansuralievich. Modeling of unproductive losses in the operation of a sorting station / *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 2020, Volume 7, Issue 2, Pages 277-290,

3. Butunov, D.B., & Bashirova, A.M. (2021). MODELING OPERATING COSTS IN SORTING STATION. *ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES*, 2(9), 445-451. (<https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-1385-2021-9-445-451>)

4. Standard technical operating process of sorting station operation. Moscow, Transport Publ., 2003, 192 pages. (In Russian)

5. Kabulov J.R. Investigation of factors affecting the duration of cooling fruits in refrigerated rolling stock / J.R. Kabulov// *Proceedings of Petersburg Transport University* - 2010. - No 2 (23). - p. 276-285

6. Kabulov J.R. Justification of the conditions of transportation of fruits and vegetables in refrigerated wagons: the example of the region of Central Asia / J.R. Kabulov// *Dissertation work of Petersburg Transport University* - 2011.

7. Mardonbek Saburov, Dilmurod Butunov, Sokijon Khudayberganov, Sunnatillo Boltaev, Muslima Akhmedova, Mukhamedjan Musaev. Determination of the optimal requirement of the number of freight wagons. *AIP Conference Proceedings* 2432, 030091 (2022). 030091-1-030091-5. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0090343>

8. Buriyev Sh., Butunov D., Pardayeva U. Non-productive time losses in sorting park operation, *The scientific heritage*, VOL 1, No 74 (74), pp. 28-31, (2021), DOI: 10.24412/9215-0365-2021-74-1-28-31

9. Бутунов, Д.Б., & Котенко, А.Г. (2018). Оценка непроизводительных потерь в работе сортировочной станции. *Известия Петербургского*

университета путей сообщения, 15(4), 498-510.

10. Butunov, D.B. (2019). Development of a technical and operational model for calculating costs when processing cars at a sorting station. *Bulletin of TashIIT: Tashkent*, (3), 181-195.

11. Butunov, D., Abdukodirov, S., Khusenov, U., & Sh, B. (2021). Methods of improving technological practices of processing of combined trains at intermediate stations. *The scientific heritage*, (67-1), 39-43.

12. Butunov, D.B. (2019). A study of the implementation of standards-time of wagons at sorting station. *Journal of Tashkent Institute of Railway Engineers*, 15(3), 165-172.

13. Butunov, D., Sh, B., Abdukodirov, S., & Musayev, M. (2022). OPERATING RESULTS OF THE SORTING STATION "CH" MODEL IN DAILY MODE. *The Scientific Heritage*, (82-1), 18-25.

14. Butunov, D., Akhmedova, M., & Sh, B. (2022). SYSTEM ANALYSIS OF UNIFORMITY OF OPERATION OF SORTING STATION "CH" IN DAILY MODE. *Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (25), 30-33.

15. Akhmedova, M.D., Butunov, D.B., & Abdukodirov, S.A. (2020). Choosing the optimal scheme of placement of thermal trains on the chart of the movement of trains. *Journal of Tashkent Institute of Railway Engineers*, 16(1), 60-67.

16. Butunov, D., Abdukodirov, S., Khusenov, U., & Sh, B. (2021). Methods of improving technological practices of processing of combined trains at intermediate stations. *The scientific heritage*, (67-1), 39-43.